

STUDY OF BIOLOGICAL TRAITS OF DIFFERENT SILKWORM HYBRIDS ON V-1 CULTIVAR OF *Morus alba*.K. D. Pawar^{1*}, P. K. Rathod¹, K. P. Budhvat¹, Y. R. Sable², D. A. Nagargoje³

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Abstract

The present investigation was conducted to study the biological traits of bivoltine silkworm hybrids on V-1 mulberry variety at Sericulture laboratory, Department of Entomology, Post Graduate Institute, Dr. P.D.K.V. Akola during 2023-2024, laid in Completely Randomized Design with seven treatments and three replications. During study, it was observed that among all the hybrids used for rearing, S8 X CSR16 found the significantly superior over the rest of other hybrids tested in case of larval duration (22.36 days), fecundity (528.00), egg hatching (97.00%), pupal duration (9.88 days) and moth emergence (96.48%), which was found statistically at par with hybrid FC2 X FC1. However, these two hybrids were found significantly superior over rest of hybrids tested. In case of fecundity (548.76) hybrid FC2 X FC1 has shown superior performance over hybrid S8 X CSR16.

Keywords: Silkworm *Bombyx mori*, *Morus alba* var. V-1, Bivoltine hybrids.

Introduction

The word Sericulture is derived from the Greek word 'sericos' meaning 'silk' and the English word 'culture' meaning 'rearing' (Bobade *et al.*, 2019). Silkworm is the caterpillar of adult silk moth. Sericulture or silk farming is the art and science of rearing of silkworms to produce raw silk and end product is silk. In general, the production of silk from Silkworm by rearing practices on commercial scale is called sericulture. Silk being an exclusive fibre and popular as "Queen of Textiles" and is well known for its natural colour, fine, strong, purity and unusual lustrous. The textile industry occupies a unique place in our country. Sericulture is intensively labour based, agro based commercially attractive economic activity. Sericulture activity is mainly practiced by the rural people in association with agriculture (Taufique *et al.*, 2021).

India is the second largest producer of silk in the world. Among the four varieties of silk produced in 2022-23, Mulberry accounted for 75.60% (27,654 MT), Tasar, 3.60% (1,318 MT), Eri 20.09% (7,349 MT) and Muga 0.71% (261MT) of the total raw silk production of 36,582 MT. The total raw silk production in the country was 36,582 MT during 2022-23 which is 4.8% higher than the production achieved during 2021-22 (34,903 MT) and around 89.7% of the annual targeted production for the year 2022-23. The bivoltine raw silk production increased substantially by 12.1% from 7,941 MT during 2021-22 to 8,904 MT during 2022-23. Further, vanya silk, which includes Tasar, Eri and Muga silks, have reduced by 1.7% during 2022-23 over 2021-22. It is mainly due to reduction in the tasar silk production during 2022-23 compared to last year. The area under mulberry has increased by 4.5% in 2022-23 compared to previous year (Anonymous 2023).

2. Material and Method

The experiment was conducted in rearing house at Sericulture Laboratory Department of Entomology, PGI, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola, during September 2023 to December 2023. The present investigation was undertaken to study the biological traits of different silkworm hybrids on V-1 variety of *Morus alba*. Disease free laying of silkworm hybrids BFC₁₀ X BFC₁, BFC₁ X BFC₁₀, TT₂₁ X TT₅₆, TT₅₆ X TT₂₁, S₈ X CSR₁₆, CSR₁₆ X S₈, FC₂ X FC₁ procured from Central Sericulture Research and Training Institute, Mysore were used as test hybrid against mulberry variety V-1 as a feed of silkworm, in present investigation.

Disease free layings (DFLs) used from Central Sericulture Research and Training Institute, Mysore were placed in 7 different trays and covered by black piece of cloth and left undisturbed for 48 hrs. for uniform growth of embryo. The rearing of silkworm races was undertaken with the use of well grown mulberry plantation of V-1, as a feed.

Krishnaswami (1978) outlined an enhanced method for silkworm rearing, which was followed in the current study. Disease-free layings (DFLs) were placed in plastic trays measuring 2'x3'. The newly hatched larvae of silkworm hybrids were nourished with freshly

chopped tender mulberry leaves of the V-1 variety. Throughout the rearing process, underweight larvae were consistently removed, and after the third moult, 200 healthy larvae per tray were retained in a replicated manner. The mulberry leaves were finely chopped into pieces ranging from 0.5 to 1.5 cm² and spread over the newly hatched worms for feeding, which repeated four times a day. The rearing trays were cleaned once after the first moult and twice after the second moult up to fourth moult.

The silkworm undergoes four moults throughout its larval growth phase, completing its growth in five stages. The interval between two moults is referred to as an 'instar', resulting in a total of 'five' instars in the silkworm's lifespan. During moulting, the worms temporarily cease feeding, and as a result, food is not provided during this period. Moulting typically takes place over a period of 20 to 30 hours. Followed by each moult, a bed disinfectant called Vijetha, applied at the rate of 4 kg per 100 DFLs to prevent diseases, and feeding resumed after a half-hour interval.

Once the silkworms reached maturity, they displayed distinct characteristics, appearing translucent with a creamy coloration. At this stage, the matured worms ceased feeding, migrated towards the edges of the trays, and initiated cocoon spinning. These matured worms were manually picked and placed on netrika for cocoon spinning. The spinning process typically occurred within a timeframe of 48 to 72 hours. The pupae remained inside the cocoon till emergence. The harvesting of cocoon was carried out on the fifth or sixth days of release of worms on netrika for spinning the cocoon. To record cocoon parameters, ten cocoons were randomly selected from each treatment for observation.

The observations were recorded on larval duration, pupal duration, fecundity, egg hatching percentage and moth emergence percentage. The data obtained were analyzed and the percentage values were transformed to angular values and analyzed, and the result obtained was interpreted.

3. Result and Discussion**3.1 Larval duration (days)**

Significantly shortest duration was showed by hybrid S8 X CSR16 (22.36 days) which was recorded as superior hybrid than rest of other tested. The next best hybrid was CSR16 X S8 (23.34 days) which was at par with several hybrids such as BFC1 X BFC10 (23.37 days), BFC10 X BFC1 (23.76 days) and hybrid TT21 X TT56 (24.05 days) followed by hybrid TT56 x TT21 (24.21 days) which was at par with hybrid FC2 X FC1 (24.77 days) which was showed highest larval duration than other tested hybrids. The results of present investigation are in line with Bobade *et al.* (2019) who recorded minimum larval duration in hybrid S8 X CSR16 (22.94 days) and Thore *et al.* (2023) also recorded 23.19 days and 25.40 days larval duration in hybrid S8 X CSR16 and hybrid FC2 X FC1 respectively.

3.2 Fecundity (no.)

Significantly highest fecundity rate observed in hybrid FC2 X FC1 (548.76) followed by hybrid S8 X CSR16 (528.00) which was at par with hybrid TT21 X TT56 (516.87). The next best fecundity rate observed in hybrid TT56 X TT21 (510.01). Hybrid CSR16 X S8 was recorded (496.86) fecundity rate which was showed at par result with hybrid BFC10 X BFC1 (485.10). The lowest fecundity observed in hybrid BFC1 X BFC10 (478.02). Trilekha *et al.* (2023) recorded 597 fecundity rates in hybrid FC2 X FC1. Similar results were observed by Mele (2023) and Khaire (2023) who reported 539 and 546 fecundity rates respectively in hybrid FC2 X FC1 in their experiment.

3.3 Hatching percentage (%)

Significantly highest hatching per cent found in hybrid S8 X CSR16 (97.00%) which was statistically at par with hybrid FC2 X FC1 (96.17%) and hybrid TT21 X TT56 (95.64%). The next best hybrid was CSR16 X S8 (94.48%) and hybrid TT56 X TT21 (94.04%) both are statistically at par with each other. Hybrid BFC10 X BFC1 (91.06%) and hybrid BFC1 X BFC10 (89.78%) which were recorded as hybrid of lowest egg hatching per cent. The above results are in accordance with Bobade *et al.* (2019) who recorded highest egg hatching per cent 97% in hybrid S8 X CSR16. Trilekha *et al.* (2024) also reported 96.82% hatching in hybrid FC2 X FC1 which was quite similar with above result.

3.4 Pupal duration (days)

The hybrid S8 X CSR16 (9.88 days) showed minimum pupal duration which was at par with hybrid CSR16 X S8 (10.28 days) both were superior over rest of other hybrids tested followed by hybrid TT21 X TT56 (10.62 days) which was at par with hybrid TT56 X TT21 (11.11 days). The maximum pupal duration was observed in hybrid BFC1 X BFC10 (11.28 days), hybrid BFC10 X BFC1 (11.59 days) and hybrid FC2 X FC1 (11.80 days). Similar findings were observed by Bobade *et al.* (2019) who reported minimum pupal duration 9.92 days in hybrid S8 X CSR16. Thore *et al.* (2023) also observed 10 days and 11.25 days pupal duration in hybrid S8 X CSR16 and hybrid FC2 X FC1 respectively. Similar findings were observed by Mele (2023) and Khaire (2023) in their research.

3.5 Moth emergence (%)

Significantly highest moth emergence per cent was found in hybrid S8 X CSR16 (96.48 per cent) which was statistically at par with group of hybrids such as FC2 X FC1 (96.00 per cent), CSR16 X S8 (95.16 per cent) and TT21 X TT56 (94.72 per cent). The next superior hybrid was TT56 X TT21 (93.02 per cent) which showed at par result with hybrid BFC10 X BFC1 (92.34 per cent) and hybrid BFC1 X BFC10 (91.50 per cent) which was recorded as hybrid of lowest moth emergence rate. The findings of present investigation are correlated with Thore *et al.* (2023) who reported 95.25% moth emergence in hybrid FC2 X FC1. Also, they observed 97% moth emergence in hybrid S8 X CSR16. Similar results were found by Mele (2023) and Khaire (2023).

Table:1. Biological traits of bivoltine silkworm hybrids on V-1 mulberry variety.

Sr. No.	Treatments	Larval duration (Days)	Fecundity	Egg Hatching %	Pupal duration (Days)	Moth Emergence %
1	BFC ₁₀ X BFC ₁	23.76	485.10	91.06 (72.63)	11.59	92.34 (73.95)
2	BFC ₁ X BFC ₁₀	23.37	478.02	89.78 (71.39)	11.28	91.50 (73.07)
3	TT ₂₁ X TT ₅₆	24.05	516.87	95.64 (78.00)	10.62	94.72 (76.78)
4	TT ₅₆ X TT ₂₁	24.21	510.01	94.04 (75.98)	11.11	93.02 (74.78)
5	S ₈ X CSR ₁₆	22.36	528.00	97.00 (80.09)	9.88	96.48 (79.26)
6	CSR ₁₆ X S ₈	23.34	496.86	94.48 (76.44)	10.28	95.16 (77.41)
7	FC ₂ X FC ₁	24.77	548.76	96.17 (78.88)	11.80	96.00 (78.58)
	SE (m) ±	0.30	4.48	1.00	0.23	1.01
	CD at 5%	0.90	13.60	3.05	0.70	3.05
	CV (%)	2.16	1.53	2.28	3.66	2.28

*Figures in parentheses indicate arc sin transformed values.

Conclusion

Among all the seven hybrids used for rearing, hybrid S8 X CSR16 showed the best results for larval duration, pupal duration, egg hatching percentage, moth emergence percentage and fecundity. Hybrid FC2 X FC1 was statistically at par with hybrid S8 X CSR16. Based on biological and overall performance it can be concluded that the bivoltine hybrid S8 X CSR16 reared on mulberry variety V-1 was found superior over all other hybrids tested under Vidarbha condition.

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